

to fertility alteration and evaluating their utility in two-line heterosis breeding were the objectives of the present investigation.

TGMS lines SA2, F61, JP8-8-1s, JP1, IC10, ID24, and JP24A identified at DRR, Hyderabad, and IR32364, IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949, received from IRRI, Philippines, were screened. These TGMS lines were grown under constant and varying temperature and daylength combination regimes in a growth chamber. They were also grown in fields under staggered sowing and ratooning over seasons. Lines SA2, JP8-8-1s, F61, IC10, and ID24 were found to be interactive with photoperiod; therefore, they are designated as PTGMS. JP1 and the TGMS lines from IRRI were more or less independent of photoperiod influence. The critical fertility point, the temperature at which maximum fertility occurred, ranged from 20 to 26 °C in various PTGMS lines and from 20 to 30 °C for other TGMS lines. The critical sterility point, the temperature at which total sterility occurred, was at 25 °C and above for PTGMS lines and at 32 °C for TGMS lines. Reverse TGMS line JP24A showed total sterility below 26 °C and complete fertility at 28 °C and above.

The temperature at which physiological sterility occurred (biological lower limit) and the temperature at which sensitivity for various lines was identified differed. PTGMS lines were stable for sterility under field conditions (March-June), whereas TGMS lines reverted back to fertility under cloudy weather and cooler night temperatures. Stable sterility in PTGMS lines may be because of the dual role of temperature and photoperiod or their interaction. Spikelet fertility under field conditions ranged from 7 to 21% and 11-70% seed set was recorded in a growth chamber for PTGMS lines. This warrants a search to identify critical areas for their seed multiplication. ■

Identifying rice genotypes with the TGMS trait suitable for north India

N. Saxena and J.P. Singh, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, India

The discovery of the environment-sensitive genic male sterility (EGMS) system laid the foundation for replacing the three-line system with the simpler and more efficient two-line system for hybrid rice seed production. EGMS includes photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) and thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) systems. The required daylength differences do not occur in our rice seasons for PGMS seed production. Therefore, we attempted to develop suitable TGMS lines in India.

We studied fertility responses to temperature in 15 TGMS lines during 1995-96 under natural environmental conditions at Pantnagar, situated at 29° N latitude, 79.3° E longitude, and 244 m above sea level. The aim was to identify suitable TGMS lines for the northwestern regions of Uttar Pradesh. The TGMS lines were sown on various planting dates and maintained in the nethouse or glasshouse.

Five TGMS lines showed seasonal fertility-sterility transformation under field conditions. These lines were characterized by sterility under high temperature (mean daily average >29 °C) and fertility transformation at low temperature (mean daily average 26-28 °C). IR68292-10-34-6, IR68292-10-34-25, and IR68949-5-31-34 were completely sterile when sown in February to April but partially fertile when planted after the second fortnight of May. IR68945-33-4-14-4 and IR68945-33-4-14-7 showed complete sterility when sown in February to May and were partially fertile when sown in June and July. IR68292-10-34-6, IR68292-10-34-25, and IR68949-5-31-34 may be exploited for hybrid seed production with off-season sowing in February to April. Seeds of these lines can be multiplied by sowing in July to August, whereas TGMS lines IR68945-33-4-14-4 and IR68945-33-4-14-7 can be used to produce hybrid seed in the main season, and parental lines can be multiplied by sowing in July and August. To exploit these lines in developing commercial hybrids, further studies are in progress to test their stability at several locations in the region and also under controlled temperature conditions. ■

Genetics

Zhenong 921: a new indica rice variety with high yield and blast resistance

Shi Chunchai, Department of Agronomy, Zhejiang Agricultural University (ZAU), Hangzhou 310029, China; Chen Wenguang, Seed Corporation of Shaoxin County, Zhejiang 312000, China; Chen Guolin, ZAU; Zhang Genxian, Agriculture Popularization Station of Kaihua County, Zhejiang 324300, China; Shen Zongtan, ZAU; and Wu Jianguo, ZAU

Zhenong 921, a new semidwarf indica rice variety, is derived from Zhongzhe 1/K 125-34 and is suitable for the double-cropped area of southern China. It was registered by Zhejiang Province in 1997 as an early rice variety.

About 2,000 ha in southern China are planted to Zhenong 921, which has a growth duration of about 109 d. Zhenong 921 has a high, stable yield potential under normal fertilization. It yielded 6.7-7.5 t ha⁻¹ in yield trials and its highest yield of 8.1 t ha⁻¹ was 9.3% more than that of the check in 1994. Its leaf blast and neck blast resistance scores were 1.6 and 1.9, compared with check Zhe 852, which scored 4.6 and 3.4, respectively. Zhenong 921 has cold resistance in the seedling stage and good lodging resistance.

Tables 1 and 2 show morpho-agronomic characters. Zhenong 921 is awnless and medium-grained. The milled rice length and the ratio of length to width are 6.5 mm and 2.5,

Table 1. Plant traits of Zhenong 921.

Year	Duration (d)	Plants	Panicles	Productive tillers (%)	Plant height (cm)
		(no. m ²)			
1994	104.9	195.0	406.5	77.4	68.9
1995	112.8	156.0	339.0	76.6	73.8
1996	109.3	162.0	411.0	73.5	80.7
Mean	109.0	171.0	385.5	75.8	74.5

Table 2. Agronomic traits of Zhenong 921.

Year	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	Fertilized grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)
1994	17.4	85.9	64.3	74.9	27.6
1995	17.6	98.3	70.6	71.8	27.6
1996	18.3	88.3	75.0	84.9	27.2
Mean	17.8	90.8	70.0	77.2	27.5

respectively. It has 83.9% brown rice recovery, 75.5% milled rice recovery, 43.9% head milled rice recovery, 26.3% amylose content, 50 mm gel

consistency, an alkali spreading value of 3, and acceptable cooking or eating quality. ■

Cytogenetics of alien chromosome addition lines in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) with single chromosomes of *O. punctata* Kotschy

H. Yasui and N. Iwata, Plant Breeding Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University, Fukuoka 812-81, Japan

Monosomic alien addition lines (MAALs) of *O. sativa* carrying single chromosomes of *O. punctata* were developed (Yasui and Iwata 1991). In the progenies of these MAALs, we identified plants in which the extra chromosome was telocentric or acrocentric.

Three monotelosomic alien addition lines (MtAALs) and one monoacrocentric alien addition line (MaAAL), each carrying single chromosomes of *O. punctata*, were isolated from the progenies of the respective MAALs for chromosomes 2, 4, 7, and 9. Mitotic and meiotic chromosomes of the MtAALs and an MaAAL were analyzed (see figure). A telosome as an extra chromosome was observed in the

respective MtAALs and one of them was for a short arm of chromosome 9. An acrocentric that consisted of a complete short arm and a heterochromatic proximal region of a long arm for chromosome 4 was observed in the MaAAL. Three MtAALs were

designated as MtAALs 2, 7, and 9S, respectively, and one MaAAL was designated as MaAAL 4S4L.

Morphology, seed fertility, and transmission of the extra chromosome of the MtAALs and the MaAAL were compared with the respective primary trisomics and MAALs. The plant morphology of MtAAL 2 and MaAAL 4S4L was similar to that of the respective MAALs, but that of MtAAL 9S was similar to disomics and that of MtAAL 7 was similar to secondary trisomics for the short arm of chromosome 7. Seed fertility of the MAAL, which ranged from 6.6% for MtAAL 2 to 94.5% for MtAAL 7, was higher than the respective primary trisomics and MAALs. The transmission rates of the extra chromosome, which ranged from 22.0% for MtAAL 2 to 28.2% for MaAAL 4S4L, were similar to those of the respective MAALs.

The mode of meiotic chromosome behavior of the MtAALs and the MaAAL was compared with that of the respective primary trisomics and MAALs (see table). The ratios of the pollen mother cells (PMCs) with a trivalent were clearly different between primary trisomics (32-67%) and

Comparison of meiotic chromosome behavior of primary trisomics and MAALs each with a single chromosome of *O. punctata*.

Trisomics/ MAAL	Number of cells			Cells with trivalent (%)
	12II+11 11II+3I ^a	11II+1III	Total	
Triplo 2	45	21	66	31.8
MAAL 2	158	5	163	3.1
MtAAL 2	26	0	26	0
Triplo 4	31	62	93	66.7
MAAL 4	171	0	171	0
MaAAL 4S4L ^b	50	0	50	0
Triplo 7	47	83	130	63.9
MAAL 7	54	0	54	0
MtAAL 7	155	1	156	0.6
Triplo 9	25	51	76	67.1
MAAL 9	60	0	60	0
MtAAL 9S ^c	41	0	41	0

^aTwo PMCs of MtAAL 2 and three PMCs of MtAAL 7 showed 11II+3I. ^bMonoacrocentric alien addition line carrying the complete short arm and the proximal long arm of chromosome 4 derived from *O. punctata*. ^cMonotelosomic alien addition line carrying the short arm of chromosome 9 derived from *O. punctata*.